

A Fallback Localization Algorithm for Automated Vehicles Based on Object Detection and Tracking

MARIO RODRÍGUEZ-ARZAMENA ^{1,2} (Member, IEEE), JOSE MATUTE ³,
JAVIER ARALUCE ¹ (Member, IEEE), LUKAS KUSCHNIG ⁴, CHRISTOPH PILZ ⁴, MARKUS SCHRATTER ⁴,
JOSHUÉ PÉREZ RASTELLI ⁵ (Member, IEEE), AND ASIER ZUBIZARRETA ²

¹TECNALIA, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), 48160 Derio, Spain

²Department of Automatic Control and Systems Engineering, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, 48013 Bilbao, Spain

³Virginia Tech Transportation Institute, 3500 Transportation Research Plaza, Blacksburg, VA 24061 USA

⁴Department of Electric, Electronic, and Software, Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, 8010 Graz, Austria

⁵CEIT-Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Donostia-San Sebastián, 20009 San Sebastián, Spain

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: MARIO RODRÍGUEZ-ARZAMENA (e-mail: mario.rodriguez@tecnalia.com).

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ABSTRACT Integrating Automated Vehicles (AVs) into everyday traffic is an ongoing challenge. Ensuring the safety of all involved agents, even in the presence of system failures, is crucial, especially in urban environments. This paper introduces a fallback-oriented localization algorithm for AVs designed to operate during main localization source failures. The method leverages stationary vehicles as dynamic landmarks, identified through the perception module, despite their initially unknown positions. By tracking relative positions before failure and applying trilateration, the algorithm estimates the ego vehicle's position. The proposed algorithm is evaluated through simulations, a real-world dataset, and practical tests on two vehicle models. The results include an average trajectory error of 0.62 m and 1.58 deg compared to the ground truth over different fallback maneuvers. This translates into an average relative translational error of 1.65% and a relative rotational error of 0.05 deg/m, improving the performance of an IMU-based dead reckoning and, hence, providing localization for performing safe stop maneuvers.

INDEX TERMS Automated vehicles, fallback, landmark localization, trilateration.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the development of Automated Vehicles (AVs) has gathered increasing attention from both the academia and industry community. AVs have gradually increased their capabilities and are closer to achieving SAE levels 4 and 5 [1].

However, the complete implementation of AVs in everyday traffic is yet to be achieved, and factors such as cost, user acceptance, and accountability remain challenges to be solved. To increase public acceptance, the safety of passengers, people in the surroundings, and infrastructure must be guaranteed. Therefore, one of the critical components that an AV must have is the capability to address complex safety-critical scenarios where automated system failures, such as

sensor failures or cybersecurity issues, can lead to dangerous situations [2], [3].

The different components of an AV are subjected to system failures or performance degradations. One of the most critical systems is perception and localization, as other systems, such as the decision and control systems, require data to operate correctly. For instance, exteroceptive sensors, e.g., Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR), cameras, radar, and Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), are used for scene understanding and ego vehicle localization but can be affected by different vulnerabilities. GNSS is subjected to issues such as low satellite visibility in urban scenarios, the multipath effect, interferences, or even external threats like jamming

or spoofing attacks [4]. Most LiDAR-based localization algorithms depend on pre-built maps, which can become outdated or obstructed [5]. Other localization techniques, such as visual odometry [6] or LiDAR odometry [7], [8], involve the continued use of more computational resources solely dedicated to this task and are also vulnerable to sensor failures. To avoid these issues, the feasibility of using Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications for solving the localization problem is explored in [9], where aspects affecting cooperative perception are examined and the quality of V2X-provided data is rated. It is determined that an error in the order of a meter can be expected in dynamic scenarios.

Consequently, robust fallback strategies for AV localization systems remain an open research area, focusing on maintaining sufficient accuracy for safe stop maneuvers in urban environments, even in the event of sensor failures. In this work, a novel fallback-oriented localization algorithm that makes use of stationary vehicles as landmarks is proposed. Hence, this approach avoids using specific-purpose landmarks but instead uses existing vehicles whose position is previously unknown. In combination with the trilateration algorithm [10], it estimates the position of the ego vehicle. This work attempts to provide a localization algorithm that is accurate enough to perform a safe stop maneuver while avoiding using computationally expensive algorithms solely dedicated to this purpose. Furthermore, an extensive evaluation of the algorithm in different domains, including simulation, dataset, and real vehicles, is carried out, demonstrating the robustness and performance of the algorithm. By leveraging stationary vehicles as landmarks, the approach proposed in this work offers a flexible and lightweight fallback solution for urban environments, addressing the limitations of existing methods that rely on complex fusion algorithms, predetermined landmark maps, or dead-reckoning techniques.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the related work to localization after sensor failures, landmark-based localization, and the use of trilateration for solving the localization problem of an autonomous robot. In Section III, the Landmark Odometry algorithm is detailed. Next, the test procedures used for validation are described in Section IV. Section V covers the description and analysis of the obtained results. Finally, Section VI gathers the conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

The literature contains works exploring different approaches to maintaining an accurate localization after the failure of one or various positioning sources. The most recurrent approach involves the fusion of data from dissimilar devices, employing Kalman filtering variants [5], [11], [12]. However, they require at least one functioning source of localization. This way, if the last localization becomes unavailable, the localization accuracy starts to rely exclusively on the quality of a dead-reckoning algorithm [13] that acts as a fallback solution for the localization. These approaches imply integrating the data from an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) considering

the mathematical model of the vehicle, which usually leads to error accumulation or drift in the short to medium term [14].

Different dead-reckoning algorithms have been proposed to reduce drift. Jonasson et al. [15] rely exclusively on proprioceptive sensors, namely an IMU, wheel speed sensors, and a pinion angle sensor to compute an emergency localization after a complete failure of the localization sources. Besides the sensors, an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) with a complex dynamic model is employed. The approach from Brossard et al. [14] to handle a GNSS outage is an IMU-based dead-reckoning that uses an EKF whose covariance noise parameters are dynamically adapted through a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The primary benefit of this approach is that it enables localization without the need for additional sensors. Matute et al. [13] addresses the issue of a localization failure through a virtual sensor based on an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF). This virtual sensor employs the odometry, the IMU measurements, and the cornering stiffness of the vehicle to provide indirect localization. Furthermore, the cornering stiffness is interpolated from a database with velocity and front-wheel angle values.

Commonly, only proprioceptive sensors are utilized to provide an alternative localization solution after the main localization source failure. However, a failure in the localization pipeline does not necessarily mean that the complete set of exteroceptive sensors becomes unavailable, leaving valuable information that could be useful. Hence, one promising approach involves leveraging external environmental features, such as landmarks, to maintain positional accuracy.

Landmark-based localization is a technique that usually involves features of the operation territory such as landmarks or road marks to solve the localization problem [16]. These landmarks are detectable and identifiable, and their location is previously known. Hence, the position of the ego vehicle can be estimated through relative measurements of these landmarks. Some examples of the literature that use this technique include Engel et al. [17], which addressed the problem using a neural network that estimates the vehicle pose from a set of lists of mapped and measured landmarks.

Regarding the type of used landmarks, pole-like ones are the most recurrent in the literature. Sefati et al. [18] uses physical objects such as trees, traffic signs, or street lamps, which are detected by specific-purpose detection algorithms and determines the ego vehicle position using a particle filter approach in combination with a prerecorded digital map. The work of Noizet et al. [19] focuses on comparing the accuracy obtained using cameras or LiDARs in the landmark detection process. The authors employ geo-referenced traffic signs, traffic lights, and street lights, and solve the map-matching as an assignment problem using the Hungarian method. In Schaefer et al. [20], the authors focus on long-term stability through a ground-truth landmarks map and a dedicated pole detection algorithm. Mimuro et al. [21] employs prerecorded snow poles to localize a vehicle on snow-covered roads using the technique of dynamic programming matching to correlate the detected poles with the map. Finally, Wang et al. [22] use

traffic lights as landmarks to solve the localization problem in intersections. Again, the ground truth position of these landmarks is previously known in a high-precision map. The traffic lights are detected and measured using a visual selective attention model, and the localization is made through an EKF combined with the IMU information.

Based on this literature analysis, it can be concluded that even if various approaches to long-term landmark-based localization exist, they all require a ground truth map of the landmarks, which may be subjected to changes over time. However, in other fields of the literature, such as uncrewed aerial vehicles, some approaches to the localization problem including mobile anchors as landmarks have been explored, in which their position is subject to uncertainty. In the work of Sorbelli et al. [23], the mobile anchors, which broadcast their position, are equipped with a GNSS, while the distance to the drone is calculated by measuring the time of flight of a wireless transmission. They use the trilateration [10] method to find the best guess of the localization. DiGiampaolo et al. [24] also employs the trilateration method to optimize the position guess of an autonomous vehicle, but using an RFID-based system of tags as landmarks. Finally, Bahr et al. [25] applies the trilateration method for localizing a robot in a subaquatic environment. The position of the beacons that serve as landmarks is subject to uncertainty and the trilateration algorithm helps reduce estimation errors.

Building on the concepts discussed, this work explores an approach that uses exteroceptive sensors to detect static vehicles as landmarks and applies the trilateration algorithm to estimate the ego vehicle position in the event of a positioning failure. Specifically, this work uses a 3D object detection algorithm based on LiDAR point clouds, although the approach is generalizable to other detection methods. As far as the authors know, there are no related works in this area.

III. LANDMARK ODOMETRY

The proposed Landmark Odometry algorithm is a lightweight localization method designed to provide emergency localization in urban environments when the main positioning source fails. Rather than enabling continuous driving, it offers a short-term fallback solution to guide the vehicle to a safe state.

The key characteristics of the proposed approach are summarized as follows:

- *Landmark-based approach:* The algorithm estimates ego vehicle positions using stationary vehicles as local reference landmarks.
- *Unknown landmark positions:* Unlike conventional landmark-based localization, the positions of landmarks are unknown beforehand and must be estimated using 3D object detection.

These characteristics enable several advantages over other localization methods:

- *Virtual Sensor:* The algorithm operates as a virtual sensor, eliminating the need for dedicated hardware.
- *Lightweight execution:* The computational load required by the algorithm is reduced, in contrast to other

localization algorithms such as Visual Odometry [6] or Simultaneous Location and Mapping (SLAM) [26].

- *Agnostic to sensor type:* The approach relies on the 3D object detection output, but is agnostic to the used sensor.

However, the method is subject to certain assumptions and constraints. The effectiveness of the Landmark Odometry depends on the presence of stationary vehicles, as moving objects are not valid and automatically discarded. Additionally, the method assumes that the failure only affects the localization capabilities (e.g. GNSS signal failure, LiDAR-based algorithm miscalculation, etc.), while other perception functions, including 3D object detection, remain fully operational. The accuracy and stability of these algorithms are critical for the performance.

Fig. 1 summarizes the proposed approach. The 3D-object detection and tracking algorithms obtain the landmark relative position to the ego vehicle. After a landmark validation procedure, the distances to the valid objects are used to compute the new ego vehicle position based on a sum of vectors. The pose is refined with the trilateration method in cases where at least three landmarks are valid. Furthermore, the ego vehicle orientation is estimated by comparing the global orientation of a landmark before localization failure with its observed orientation in the local ego vehicle frame.

A. LANDMARK COLLECTION

As previously detailed, the first step is to detect and collect existing landmarks using 3D object detection and tracking approaches.

Most 3D detection algorithms work in the local ego vehicle frame but without memory [27]. This means that, in each instant, the scene is analyzed, without considering the detections of previous iterations. Consequently, the algorithm cannot identify whether a vehicle detection corresponds to the same vehicle in different moments, which is a key requirement of Landmark Odometry.

By contrast, tracking algorithms solve this problem [28]. They allow the vehicle to identify whether the detections made in consecutive iterations correspond to the same vehicle and to calculate some kinematic properties such as the velocities and accelerations of the surrounding objects. Most of them work in the map frame (a global reference axis) and need the position and velocities of the ego vehicle as input. While this is not problematic during the normal operation of the main localization sources, it causes a paradox during the execution of the Landmark Odometry: One of the needed inputs for the execution, the position of the surrounding stationary vehicles in the ego vehicle frame along successive iterations, is given by an algorithm needing the ego vehicle position to work, which is the unknown variable that the algorithm is trying to estimate.

The workaround uses the previously calculated ego vehicle position as input for the tracking algorithm. This means that, in the first iteration after the main localization source failure, the last reliable position and velocities are given to the tracking algorithm, which then computes the new positions of the

FIGURE 1. An overview of the proposed Landmark Odometry algorithm. The method uses 3D object detection and tracking from the AV’s perception module to collect and extract landmarks. Then the position of the vehicle is computed with a sum of vectors and applying the trilateration algorithm, if possible, where the yaw is estimated by comparing the global orientation of the landmarks with its observed orientation in the local ego vehicle frame.

surrounding vehicles and allows the Landmark Odometry to compute one first iteration. Then, this solution of the Landmark Odometry is given as the input for the next tracking iteration. Even though it theoretically solves the problem, the inherent inaccuracies of the 3D detection and tracking algorithms quickly introduce rising and accumulative errors. Consequently, the final workaround consists of assuming an error in the tracking algorithm once the Landmark Odometry starts working and using a combination of the strengths of both 3D detection and tracking algorithms.

In this work, a modification of the Autoware Multi-Object Tracker [29] is proposed, which allows the modification of the local frame of the ego vehicle to the output of the Landmark Odometry, instead of using the one produced by the main localization algorithm.

B. LANDMARK VALIDATION

As mentioned, a 3D detection algorithm gives the classified detections locally, without either kinematic information or a unique identification. It determines whether the detection is a car, a pedestrian, or a truck, but it does not know whether the detected object is the same as in previous iterations. On the other hand, the tracking algorithms start accumulating errors after the main localization source failure, associating the detections to the same physical object in different iterations, and providing kinematic information. Therefore, as illustrated in Fig. 2, the proposed procedure is as follows:

- Before the failure of the main localization source:
 - The 3D detection and the tracking algorithms work normally, detecting vehicles that belong to the “Car”, “Bus”, “Truck” or “Trailer” categories.
 - Filtering by the velocity given by the tracking module, the vehicles that are not stationary are discarded.
 - The valid tracked objects are converted to the local ego vehicle frame.
- After the failure of the main localization source:

FIGURE 2. Flow diagram of the landmark collection and validation.

- The 3D detection and tracking algorithms continue working, but the tracking uses the previous output of the Landmark Odometry as the ego vehicle position (the last valid position from the main localization source is used in the first iteration).
- The objects are cross-checked by the Universally Unique Identifier (UUID). If the current tracked vehicles list does not share, at least, one UUID with the tracked vehicles of the previous iteration, the Landmark Odometry algorithm cannot proceed and cannot compute a valid solution.
- Then, filtering by the velocity given by the tracking module, non-stationary vehicles are discarded.
- The valid tracked objects are converted to the local ego vehicle frame.
- The detected objects are associated with valid tracked objects based on their Euclidean distance. If a tracked object is within two meters of a detected object, they

FIGURE 3. Fundamentals behind Landmark Odometry. The black vehicle corresponds to the ego vehicle in the current instant. The gray vehicle represents the last position of the ego vehicle before the failure of the main localization source, and the blue vehicles are the stationary vehicles used as landmarks. (a) Initialization of the algorithm with the main localization source working. (b) Generalization of the position of the ego vehicle in $t = t_n$, given the last known position of the ego vehicle, the position of the landmark in the local frame that instant, and the new position of the landmark in the local frame. (c) Landmark Odometry at a given instant $t = t_{n+1}$. (d) Generalization of the addition of a new landmark. (e) Generalization of the addition of new landmarks after the loss of the original landmarks.

are assumed to represent the same object. By leveraging the spatial volume of objects used as landmarks, this approach helps mitigate most positioning errors, as the detections are performed in the local frame.

- A list of valid landmarks is generated, containing the UUID of the tracked object but the pose information (position of the centroid and orientation) of the corresponding detected object.

C. SUM OF VECTORS

Once the valid landmarks are calculated, the sum of vectors can be executed. The fundamental idea behind Landmark Odometry relies on a sum of vectors as illustrated in Fig. 3(a)–(e), a sequence of events used to describe the approach, where the **black** vehicle represents the ego vehicle, and the **blue** vehicle corresponds to a parked vehicle.

While the main localization source is operating properly $t = t_0$ (Fig. 3(a)), the ego vehicle position from the nominal localization algorithm is considered to be the closest guess to the ground truth that can be achieved. This position can be represented as a vector \vec{a} , with the origin in the map frame.

As previously detailed, the automated ego vehicle is assumed to have functional 3D object detection and tracking algorithms, which are needed for the decision algorithms to determine the appropriate maneuver. In the ego vehicle frame, the vector that represents the obstacle (stationary vehicle), or in this case, the landmark position, is defined as \vec{b} . In $t = t_n$ (Fig. 3(b)) the main localization source fails and becomes unavailable, and the new ego vehicle position \vec{a}' can be calculated as:

$$\vec{a}' = \vec{a} + \vec{b} - \vec{c} \quad (1)$$

where \vec{a} is the last known ego vehicle position in $t = t_0$, \vec{b} corresponds to the parked vehicle (landmark) position in $t = t_0$, and \vec{c} represents the new position in the ego vehicle frame of the parked vehicle in $t = t_n$.

In the next instant $t = t_{n+1}$ (Fig. 3(c)), \vec{a} and \vec{b} remain the positions of the ego vehicle and the parked vehicle when the main localization source was available. Thus, no additional error is added in comparison to the previous iteration.

New detected vehicles can be added as landmarks during the execution of the Landmark Odometry, as long as there is landmark continuity between iterations. This is known as tracked vehicle continuity, and it is critical to maintain the relationship to at least one of the landmarks obtained during the correct operation of the main localization source. A metaphor would be a monkey that needs vine continuity between trees to continue moving. A graphical representation is illustrated in Fig. 3(d), associated to $t = t_{n+2}$. This means that as long as at least one landmark that was visible at $t = t_0$, when the failure occurred, is still visible at $t = t_{n+2}$, newly detected vehicles can be used as landmarks, since the relative position between this new landmark and the previous one \vec{d}_{12} is known.

Furthermore, this approach is generalizable. As depicted in Fig. 3(e), if at $t = t_{n+3}$ there are no remaining visible landmarks from $t = t_0$, but there are some detected at $t = t_{n+2}$ when the former were visible, new landmarks can be added following the same procedure as long as a previously used landmark is still being tracked.

Unlike dead-reckoning algorithms, which inherently accumulate error over time due to sensor drift, Landmark Odometry depends primarily on three factors: the accuracy of the landmarks at the moment the primary localization source is disconnected, the detection accuracy when a new landmark is added (both resulting in non-recoverable error), and the detection accuracy at each subsequent timestamp (contributing to recoverable error).

Therefore, one novelty of the algorithm is to employ parked vehicles as landmarks, whose localization is previously unknown, instead of using purpose-specific landmarks, which need to be installed in the operation territory, and require additional detection and identification methods.

D. TRILATERATION

Commonly, various valid landmarks can be found at every iteration. If there are two or fewer, the sum of vectors approach is executed using the landmark whose detection had the best-given accuracy (metric directly given by the detection algorithm). On the other hand, when there are three or more landmarks, the trilateration algorithm can be applied.

FIGURE 4. Representation of the trilateration. The black vehicle represents the ego vehicle, and the red dot represents the exact position of the ego vehicle frame. The blue vehicles represent the landmarks, and the blue circumferences represent the distances from the ego vehicle to each landmark, centered on the latter. (a) Represents an ideal trilateration, where the circumferences intersection matches the ego vehicle frame. (b) Represents a real trilateration, where the circumferences intersection does not match the ego vehicle frame.

The trilateration algorithm is used in GNSS to compute the receptor position by searching for the intersection of spheres with the center at each satellite and the radius being the distance from the satellite to the receptor. This same concept is used in the Landmark Odometry. The receptor is the ego vehicle, whereas the satellites are the landmarks. Ideally, if all landmarks were perfectly detected, the position of the ego vehicle would be the intersection point of the circumferences drawn centered at each landmark with the radius being the distance given by the 3D detection algorithm, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a).

However, the reality is not ideal, and the landmarks detections are not perfect. These detections can present errors in both the estimated distance to the landmark and its position. These imperfections are translated into circumferences with erroneous radii and circumferences not centered in the real position of the landmark. Consequently, the execution of the trilateration with real data is similar to Fig. 4(b), where there is no point of intersection between all the circumferences.

When the trilateration algorithm cannot be executed due to the presence of two or fewer landmarks, these imprecisions are inevitable. By contrast, with three or more landmarks, the problem is solved using a least squares optimization using the Trust Region Reflective algorithm [30]. The estimated position is given by the point (x_g, y_g) that minimizes the sum of the least squares:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_i^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \left\{ (x_i - x_g)^2 + (y_i - y_g)^2 + \lambda_i^2 = (r_i - r_g)^2 \right. \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

where $i \in \{1, N\}$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$, and represents the i th landmark. N corresponds to the number of valid landmarks, x_i and y_i represent the coordinates of the i th landmark, r_i represents the Euclidean distance from the ego vehicle to the i th landmark,

FIGURE 5. Yaw estimation. The blue car represents a landmark and the green car represents the current position of the ego vehicle. The orientation of the ego vehicle in the global frame is given by the difference between the orientation of the landmark in the global frame and the detection in the ego vehicle local frame.

while x_g , y_g and r_g correspond to the estimated values. Furthermore, the sum of residuals is used as an indicator of the performance of the algorithm and is reflected in the covariance matrix.

To further refine the landmark odometry results, a distance-based filter is applied. Specifically, the algorithm checks the Euclidean distance between the newly calculated position and the previous iteration's result. If this distance exceeds three meters, the new result is discarded, regardless of whether it was obtained through vector summation or trilateration. This filtering step is crucial, as a single faulty calculation significantly impacts the tracking algorithm and, in turn, compromises the validation of subsequent landmarks.

E. YAW ESTIMATION BY COMPARISON

Until now, the solution has only solved the estimation of X and Y coordinates, but the localization problem also involves orientations. Since the algorithm is meant to execute fallback maneuvers during limited driving time, the angle estimation problem can be simplified to the yaw estimation, i.e., the angle around the Z axis.

The approach consists of the comparison between the global landmark orientation in the last iteration before the main localization source disconnection and the orientation of the detection in the local ego vehicle frame at each iteration. A graphical representation is made in Fig. 5, where the blue car represents a landmark and the green car represents the current position of the ego vehicle. There are three coordinate systems: The black one represents the global map frame. The angle of the landmark relative to it, represented by δ and the brown arc, is given by the tracking algorithm, while the angle of the ego vehicle relative to the global map frame, γ and purple arc, is the variable that is being solved. The orange coordinate axis represents the local frame of the landmark, and the green coordinate axis represents the local ego vehicle frame. The angle of the landmark seen in the local ego vehicle frame is given by the 3D detection algorithm and is represented by ρ and the red arc. The difference between them corresponds to the yaw angle of the ego vehicle in the global

map frame, represented by γ and the purple arc:

$$\gamma = \delta - \rho \quad (3)$$

The angle calculation is made with every valid landmark and the result is averaged to reduce noise. Additionally, any calculated angle that deviates by more than 15 deg from the previously averaged yaw estimate is rejected. This mechanism allows the system to tolerate single erroneous calculations without affecting the overall performance.

As a result, the localization problem is fully solved, and a complete localization containing X , Y , and yaw values γ . As aforementioned, the only requirement for the algorithm to work after the main localization source failure is the presence of static vehicles that can be detected and used as landmarks.

IV. TEST PROCEDURES

The performance of the proposed fallback localization algorithm has been evaluated in four urban scenarios, including one simulated environment, two real environments, and a real-world dataset, with different vehicles performing various maneuvers. Nevertheless, some common procedures are shared: In all scenarios, the ego vehicle starts driving with a functioning main localization source and some static vehicles inside its sensing range. At a given point, the main localization source is disconnected. Afterward, the localization is computed only using the Landmark Odometry algorithm, while the main localization source is used as the best guess of the Ground Truth. During the execution of the test procedures, the ego vehicle is driven manually.

On the sensor level, the object detection is made with a LiDAR-based object detector, using the Centerpoint [31] implementation of Autoware Universe [32].

The Landmark Odometry algorithm is executed at 10 Hz, equaling the execution frequency of the used 3D object detection algorithm. A higher frequency would elevate the computational consumption and would not produce different results since it would work with the same inputs.

The experiments were conducted on a computer running Ubuntu 22.04, equipped with a 13th Gen Intel Core i9-13980HX CPU (5.60 GHz, 24 cores, 32 threads), an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 GPU (16 GB GDDR6), and 64 GB of DDR5 RAM.

A. SIMULATION

The simulation tests are performed using the CARLA simulator [33], where a custom scenario is created. This scenario is shown in Fig. 6. It consists of a four-lane urban road with parked vehicles on both sides. In this scenario, the ego vehicle drives at speeds from 10 to 20 km/h, and 72 km/h. The Landmark Odometry is evaluated by considering the most common urban behaviors through the following maneuvers: straight-lane driving, lane change, pull-out at the shoulder, and stopped vehicle in lane avoidance, as shown in Fig. 7.

The localization ground truth of the ego vehicle comes from the simulator without any additional error. In addition, the ego vehicle is equipped with a 32-channel LiDAR.

FIGURE 6. Initial CARLA setup. The LiDAR is simulated to be equipped on the top center of the vehicle.

FIGURE 7. Executed maneuvers. (a) Straight-lane driving. (b) Lane change. (c) Pull-out at the shoulder. (d) Stopped vehicle in lane avoidance.

B. DATASET

The dataset tests comprise the KITTI Odometry dataset [34]. More precisely, the evaluation is performed in some fragments of Sequence 00, including straight driving and soft turns. The vehicle is equipped with a Velodyne HDL-64E LiDAR, and the evaluation is made against the localization ground truth of the dataset, which is the output of a GNSS/IMU localization unit (OXTS RT 3003) mounted on the vehicle.

C. REAL-WORLD

Two different real-world scenarios are used for evaluation. The first is done in a private testing track at Tecalia, replicating the maneuvers of the simulation scenario described in Section IV-A using a Renault Twizy. However, the experiments were carried out with significantly fewer parked vehicles. The vehicle was equipped with a Velodyne VLP-16 LiDAR on the roof, as shown in Fig. 8. Considering the GNSS-denied driving environment at the testing track, a Normal Distribution Transform (NDT) pointcloud-based algorithm [35] combined with an EKF-based algorithm from Autoware Universe, was employed as the best approximation to the localization Ground Truth.

The second experimental tests were performed with a Ford Fusion equipped with an Ouster OS2-128 and three Ouster OS1-64, as depicted in Fig. 9. The complete sensor setup is detailed in [36], [37], and also includes six cameras, eight radars and a GNSS, although they are not used in this experiment. Similarly to the Renault Twizy experiment, the

FIGURE 8. Initial Renault Twizy setup. The LiDAR position is highlighted with a blue circle.

FIGURE 9. Initial Ford Fusion setup. The blue circle highlights the OS2-128 LiDAR, and the green circles highlight two of the OS1-64 LiDARs. The remaining OS1-64 is located at the front bottom part of the vehicle.

best approximation to the localization Ground Truth is made through Autoware Universe, using the NDT algorithm in combination with an EKF. The experiments are made on the premises of the Graz University of Technology Inffeldgasse campus at speeds around 10 to 15 km/h, with parked vehicles on both sides of the road at different angles (parallel and perpendicular). The principal particularities of this scenario are the presence of non-stationary vehicles that need to be identified as such to allow the correct execution of the algorithm, and the presence of vehicles parked with different angles, which evaluates the robustness of the angle calculation. The maneuvers performed in this experiment are composed of straight driving and a 90° left turn.

V. RESULTS

The evaluation results for all the scenarios and maneuvers are presented in this section. The Absolute Trajectory Error (ATE) [38] is used as a metric to evaluate the performance under the different scenarios introduced in Section IV. The ATE is shown in (4) for position, and in (5) for rotation.

$$ATE_{pos} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (x_g^t - x_{GT}^t)^2 + (y_g^t - y_{GT}^t)^2} \quad (4)$$

FIGURE 10. Lane change maneuver in CARLA. Position over time with tracked vehicles.

$$ATE_{rot} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (\gamma_g^t - \gamma_{GT}^t)^2} \quad (5)$$

where T is the total number of timestamps, x_g , y_g , and γ_g refer, respectively, to the X and Y coordinates and the yaw angle in each timestamp t , and x_{GT}^t , y_{GT}^t and γ_{GT}^t refer to the ground truth in each timestamp. Besides, the standard deviation for the positional and rotational errors is also presented. Table 1 shows the complete set of experiments with the corresponding results. It contains the type of testing environment, the executed maneuver, the distance traveled, the average speed during the execution of the experiment, the position ATE (ATE_{pos}) with the standard deviation, the relative translational error (t_{rel}), the rotation ATE (ATE_{rot}) with the standard deviation, the relative rotational error (r_{rel}) and the maximum and minimum number of available tracked vehicles during the whole experiment.

A. SIMULATION

Figs. 10 and 11 show the position and the yaw error over time for the CARLA simulator-based results. In Fig. 10, a red dot in (0,0) represents the point at which the main localization source is deactivated. Before this point, the landmark odometry line mimics the ground truth, but after the disconnection of the main localization source, it starts representing the output of the landmark odometry. The configuration of tracked vehicles is also represented with green dots. Note that these points belong to the outputs of the tracking algorithm and, consequently, the same vehicle can produce distinct but close points over time. Hence, these tracked vehicles are not necessarily valid landmarks.

As shown in Fig. 10, the computed localization successfully follows the simulation ground truth, even with small deviations in the position of the tracked vehicles over time. As

TABLE 1. Validation Results in the Different Environment and Maneuvers

Environment	Maneuver	Distance [m]	Avg. Speed [km/h]	ATE _{pos} ± (std) [m]	t _{rel} [%]	ATE _{rot} ± (std) [deg]	r _{rel} [deg/m]	Tracked Vehicles
Simulation	Straight lane	45.07	11.06	0.19±(0.09)	0.42	0.69±(0.40)	0.02	[18-7]
Simulation	Lane change	31.75	15.43	0.15±(0.06)	0.47	1.01±(0.50)	0.03	[18-8]
Simulation	Pull out	30.68	11.48	0.39±(0.17)	1.27	1.48±(0.81)	0.05	[18-7]
Simulation	Avoidance	18.57	18.50	0.17±(0.07)	0.92	1.07±(0.37)	0.06	[17-7]
Simulation	Straight lane	46.01	72.23	0.44±(0.21)	0.96	1.10±(0.33)	0.02	[18-7]
Simulation distance-weighted average				0.28	0.78	1.04	0.03	
Dataset	Straight lane	59.84	29.54	0.81±(0.50)	1.35	1.17±(0.91)	0.02	[12-4]
Dataset	Soft left turn	40.49	28.72	0.78±(0.39)	1.93	1.99±(1.30)	0.05	[9-3]
Dataset distance-weighted average				0.80	1.58	1.5	0.03	
Renault Twizy	Straight lane	20.31	11.01	0.56±(0.25)	2.76	0.91±(0.45)	0.04	[7-4]
Renault Twizy	Lane change	27.12	9.28	0.32±(0.18)	1.18	1.40±(0.99)	0.05	[8-2]
Renault Twizy	Pull out	15.01	8.38	0.52±(0.28)	3.46	2.05±(1.11)	0.14	[8-3]
Renault Twizy	Avoidance	19.05	8.81	0.51±(0.31)	2.68	1.62±(0.82)	0.09	[7-3]
Renault Twizy	Straight lane	36.53	27.46	0.67±(0.43)	1.83	2.31±(1.28)	0.06	[6-3]
Renault Twizy distance-weighted average				0.53	2.19	1.72	0.07	
Ford Fusion	Straight lane	60.99	11.43	1.32±(0.56)	2.16	1.97±(1.59)	0.03	[7-1]
Ford Fusion	90 deg left turn	21.18	11.20	0.97±(0.46)	4.58	4.38±(2.08)	0.21	[7-1]
Ford Fusion distance-weighted average				1.23	2.79	2.59	0.08	
Total distance-weighted average				0.62	1.65	1.58	0.05	

FIGURE 11. Lane change maneuver in CARLA. Yaw error over time.

gathered in Table 1, the ATE_{pos} is maintained at 15cm with a low standard deviation. The evolution of the yaw error is shown in Fig. 11. The corresponding ATE_{rot} is maintained at 1.01 degrees, but the standard deviation of the error reaches 0.5 degrees. Even though the calculation is noisy, it gives a good approximation to the real yaw values. As explained in

Section III-C, the proposed method can partially recover from detection errors.

The obtained results show the overall efficacy of the proposed method. The simulation set of experiments achieves the lowest errors, both for positional and rotational ATE. The main reason behind this is the dependence on the quality of the detections. The available sensor models in simulation environments present differences to the real devices, being the latter more dispersed [39]. Hence, the distance-dependent density of the LiDAR point cloud decreases the detection performance. Provided with a rich quantity of vehicles that qualify as landmarks, the algorithm is capable of maintaining average errors below 0.4 m and 1.5 deg. Furthermore, the test done at more than 70 km/h shows that performance is not subjected to the speed of the ego vehicle, but to the quality of the landmarks, as aforementioned.

B. DATASET

The overall results of the set of experiments based on real-world data using the KITTI dataset are displayed in Table 1. The proposed method can maintain an ATE around 0.8 m for

FIGURE 12. KITTI on straight lane. Position over time with tracked vehicles.

FIGURE 13. KITTI on a straight lane. Yaw error.

distances between 40 and 60 m, limiting the yaw error below 2 deg.

Fig. 12 displays the evolution of the vehicle position over time on the straight lane scene. During the first part of the maneuver, the ego vehicle detects and tracks vehicles used as landmarks. However, as the maneuver progresses, the quantity of tracked vehicles is reduced, directly impacting the localization accuracy. In the final part of the maneuver, the algorithm solely relies on a few valid landmarks already about 30 meters behind, translating to the eventual disruption of the landmark odometry output. The same effect is present in the yaw error of Fig. 13, starting to increase in the last part of the experiment.

C. REAL-WORLD

As introduced in Section IV-C, the real-world experiments are carried out in two different platforms: a Renault Twizy and a Ford Fusion.

The experiments on the Renault Twizy mimic maneuvers done in simulation. Compared to the simulation experiments, the results in Table 1 show a bigger position ATE in all maneuvers. This is caused by the decreased perception accuracy of

FIGURE 14. Renault Twizy on avoidance maneuver. Position over time with tracked vehicles.

FIGURE 15. Renault Twizy on avoidance maneuver. Yaw error over time.

real sensors. However, the position ATE is maintained around 50 cm with moderate standard deviations. The rotational ATE is also increased with respect to the simulation experiments but is still kept at low values.

Fig. 14 shows the position over time for the avoidance of a stopped vehicle maneuver. The ego vehicle receives in this experiment a variable range of tracked vehicles from seven to three. The results show how the algorithm is capable of providing good accuracy while overtaking the vehicle, and only at the end starts drifting from the ground truth values. A similar effect is present in the yaw error of Fig. 15, where the highest error values are found towards the final moments of the maneuver.

On the other hand, a set of experiments have been carried out using a Ford Fusion. These present the biggest translational and rotational ATEs.

Fig. 16 shows that the environment is rich in tracked vehicles behind the initial position, but has very few afterward, obtaining an ATE of 0.97 m. Besides, Fig. 17 shows errors that surpass 4 deg. Consequently, the execution of the trilateration method is jeopardized. This effect is shown in Fig. 18, which

FIGURE 16. Ford Fusion on a straight lane. Position over time with tracked vehicles.

FIGURE 17. Ford Fusion on a straight lane. Yaw error over time.

displays in the upper part the quantity of tracked vehicles in blue, and the number of valid landmarks in each moment in orange. The lower part of the figure shows the Euclidean error of the landmark odometry. The graphic clearly shows how the execution of the trilateration algorithm, whose limit is marked with the red dotted line, is not always possible, and there are large periods in which it is unavailable. Some periods, such as at $t = 8$ s and $t = 15$ s, correspond with the highest error peaks. Besides, at some points, only one vehicle passes the filter to be considered a landmark. Without this single vehicle, the algorithm could not continue operating. A similar effect is present in the yaw error of Fig. 17, where the highest errors mainly correspond to the moments with fewer valid landmarks. This scarcity of valid landmarks, particularly in the latter part of the experiment where trilateration cannot be applied, is the primary factor contributing to the increased ATE observed in the Ford Fusion scenario.

FIGURE 18. Ford Fusion on a straight lane. Correlation between positioning error and number of available and used landmarks.

TABLE 2. Comparison of the Metrics of the Different Methods, With the Validation Environment (S: Simulation, D: Dataset, R: Real) and the Additional Requirements

Work	Env.	Requirements	t_{rel} [%]	ATE_{pos} [m]
IMLS-SLAM [7]	D	LiDAR	0.33	-
Low-Cost Sensor Fusion [11]	R	GNSS, IMU, Camera, Map	-	1.18
Multi-sensor fusion [12]	R	GNSS, IMU, LiDAR	-	0.07
IMU Baseline [14]	D	IMU	[5.78-12.6]	-
AI-IMU [14]	D	CNN, IMU	[1.32-1.57]	-
Inertial navigation [15]	R	IMU, Wheel Speed, Pinion Angle	-	[1-3]
Ours	S+D+R	3D Object Detection	1.65	0.62

D. DISCUSSION

Results show how the proposed algorithm maintains a good localization accuracy for several seconds when sufficient vehicles can be used as landmarks.

The proposed algorithm achieves an average distance-weighted translation relative error of 1.65% and an ATE_{pos} of 0.62 m. As shown in Table 2, the proposed method is outperformed by algorithms involving additional sensors and computational resources, such as in [7], [12], [14]. Nevertheless, the aim of the proposed algorithm is not to compete with these localization algorithms, but to maintain a simplified approach that provides enough accuracy to execute the fallback maneuver. Thus, it must be compared to dead reckoning approaches. Comparing with the IMU-only baseline of [14], the Landmark Odometry achieves a significant improvement with a relative translational error lower by 4%. Similarly, the method achieves a better ATE_{pos} than in [15], although those tests were made at higher speeds.

The average execution time of the proposed algorithm, on the hardware specified in Section IV, excluding the 3D object detection and tracking processes, ranges from 1 ms with 3

landmarks to 2 ms with 16 landmarks. This execution time is approximately an order of magnitude faster than most methods listed in the KITTI Odometry benchmark, although the comparison is made with different hardware. Furthermore, it was found that the proposed algorithm's execution time is comparable to alternative fallback methods that require at least one functioning source of localization, such as those proposed in [11], [13].

Consequently, the compromise between accuracy and computational load makes the Landmark Odometry suitable for scenarios where safety is a priority over the continuous availability of the service, and the available hardware and computational load are limited due to cost or size and cannot be dedicated to execute a full localization algorithm such as SLAM [7] (e.g. small vehicles equipped with GNSS and a LiDAR only for 3D object detection). However, in scenarios where a more comprehensive and accurate localization solution is required, and computational resources are not a limitation, SLAM-based approaches may be a better option.

E. ERROR ANALYSIS

In addition to evaluating the algorithm's performance metrics, it is crucial to identify the sources of error that can affect its accuracy. These errors can be broadly categorized into three main types: Accuracy of the 3D object detection and tracking algorithms, the quantity of available landmarks, and propagation errors.

The quality of the output 3D object detection and tracking algorithms may impact the overall performance. This dependency is especially reflected in the differences between simulation and real-world experiments. In the simulation, the LiDAR is simulated with an unrealistic and more stable physical model, which enhances the performance of the detection algorithm. By contrast, in real-world experiments, noise and the spread of the LiDAR point cloud decrease the detection performance, creating instabilities in the landmarks' positions. These differences produce a difference in performance between the simulation and the Renault Twizy experiments.

The quantity of landmarks has also been a critical factor in localization accuracy. More precisely, the capability of using the trilateration method greatly impacts the overall performance. It has been demonstrated how the sum of vectors using only one vehicle as a landmark is usually translated into a quicker rise of the positional and rotational errors. However, when available, using various vehicles as reference points allows for compensating faulty measurements through the trilateration method. From a real-world implementation perspective, this limits the usability of the algorithm to urban scenarios with several parked vehicles.

The last sources of errors are the ones introduced during the landmark propagation using the procedure detailed in Fig. 3. The proposed localization algorithm can mitigate certain errors over time, specifically, those associated with the detection accuracy during operation. This is possible because the detected and tracked landmarks' positions are referenced to the last reliable ego vehicle localization output. Hence, each

iteration of the landmark localization output has a reduced impact on the performance. However, errors introduced when adding landmarks are non-recoverable and persist throughout the localization process. These errors are a combination of the 3D object detection and tracking accuracy, as well as the accuracy of the landmark odometry when adding a new landmark. Ultimately, it affects the long-term accuracy and reliability of the algorithm.

Fig. 19 shows a detailed breakdown of the different produced errors for the simulated pull-out maneuver. The selection of the simulated environment allows the evaluation of the detection and tracking performance against the ground truth. Besides, this scenario is selected due to the relatively high ATE_{Pos} compared to the other simulated maneuvers.

During the first part of the execution, all tracked vehicles were already tracked before the main localization source failure. Therefore, there is a reduced error as the landmarks do not have additional errors besides the tracking accuracy. At $t = A$, the yaw rate rises, which means that the vehicle begins to execute the pull-out maneuver. Due to the quick change of the yaw rate, the tracking module loses accuracy due to the unexpected movement from the ego vehicle, which is translated into an increment of about 30cm in the Euclidean error of the Landmark odometry. However, the tracking error is quickly reduced after the turn due to the predominance of the vehicles tracked before the failure.

During the final stage of the maneuver, the ratio between the vehicles tracked before and after the localization failure is closer, thereby increasing the influence of the latter in the overall output. The newly introduced landmarks exhibit a higher positioning error in comparison to the previous ones due to the propagation effect, hence increasing the magnitude of the error. At $t = B$ and $t = C$, new changes in the yaw rate produce an increment in the tracking error, that now has a bigger influence on the Landmark Odometry error. Consequently, the error is not able to recover to the previous values and stabilizes around 50cm.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper has introduced, verified, and validated a lightweight fallback-oriented localization algorithm for AVs in urban scenarios after the failure of the main localization source. This algorithm is based on the detection and tracking of previously unmapped stationary vehicles, which are then used as landmarks. The relative position of these landmarks to the ego vehicle is then used to compute the consequent ego vehicle poses.

Furthermore, the proposed algorithm is sensor agnostic. It uses information that is already present in an AV software stack, such as 3D object detection and tracking, instead of needing the execution of a completely dedicated and more computationally expensive localization algorithm, such as visual odometry.

It is also relevant to mention that the proposed localization algorithm is not envisioned to allow a continuous operation of the endangered ego vehicle but to provide enough

FIGURE 19. Error breakdown after the localization failure for the simulated pull-out maneuver. The first subplot shows the average detection and tracking errors. The second shows the Euclidean error of the Landmark Odometry. The third shows the yaw rate, measured with respect to the ground truth, i.e. the derivative of the yaw angle. The fourth shows the evolution of the number of vehicles tracked before the failure and those tracked after.

localization capabilities to safely execute a fallback maneuver that completes the transition into a safe state, without the need of immediately stopping the vehicle. By serving as a backup mechanism, the algorithm strengthens the overall localization stack, enhancing safety. This added resilience helps mitigate the risks associated with sudden localization failures, reducing the likelihood of abrupt vehicle stops that could create

hazardous situations. Consequently, this approach has the potential to improve user trust and acceptance by ensuring that temporary localization failures do not immediately compromise vehicle operation.

The manuscript includes an extensive set of validation tests on three different domains and using four different environments. Hence, it has been evaluated in simulation, in a real-world dataset, and two real-world vehicles under various maneuvers. The results of these tests have demonstrated the performance of the proposed method as a fallback maneuver enabler for situations where the main localization source becomes unavailable or unreliable, but the safety of the vehicle and the surroundings still need to be maintained. Overall, the results include a distance-weighted average position ATE of 0.62 m and a rotation ATE of 1.58 deg, while the relative errors are 1.65% and 0.05 deg/m for position and rotation, respectively.

The validation tests across the different domains have shown the capabilities of the proposed algorithm to maintain a good localization accuracy for a limited time, enabling the execution of a fallback maneuver. However, they have also evidenced the potential challenges that the algorithm may face in real-world deployments. It is highly dependent on the good accuracy of the 3D detection algorithm, which can be affected in varying environmental conditions (e.g. rain, fog, lack of light), and eventually decrease the Landmark Odometry capability to maintain safety. Other possible challenges are the same that affect the detection algorithms (e.g. occlusions, noisy false positives, etc.), and the dependency of the scene. Factors such as the scarcity of parked vehicles or valid landmarks starting to move could reduce or even eliminate the usefulness of the algorithm as a fallback component.

Future work could explore integrating a variation of the Kalman Filter to enhance performance by smoothing the calculated odometry and incorporating a vehicle dynamic model. However, this was not included in the present study, as the focus was on demonstrating the standalone performance of the proposed algorithm. Another potential improvement for increasing stability involves updating the landmarks using a Markov process to account for dynamic uncertainties.

Additionally, further studies could evaluate the algorithm's robustness in more diverse and challenging environments for 3D object detection, such as adverse weather conditions (e.g., rain, fog) or poor lighting. Testing in these conditions would provide insights into the method's limitations and potential adaptations.

Another important direction is the integration of Landmark Odometry with other localization methods, even in scenarios where no localization failures occur. By fusing it with existing approaches, the algorithm could contribute to a more robust localization system that enhances overall reliability. Furthermore, the algorithm's performance could be examined when deployed as the primary localization module of an autonomous vehicle, particularly in cases where the control module directly relies on landmark odometry for executing fallback maneuvers.

Finally, an extension of the algorithm to handle dynamic environments, such as traffic jams, could be explored. In such scenarios, vehicles initially used as stationary landmarks may begin to move, requiring adaptive landmark management to maintain reliable localization.

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MARIO RODRÍGUEZ-ARAZAMENA (Member, IEEE) received the B.S. degree in industrial electronics and automation engineering and the M.S. degree in control engineering, automation, and robotics from the University of the Basque Country, Leioa, Spain, in 2020 and 2022, respectively, where he is currently working toward the Ph.D. degree in control engineering, automation, and robotics. Since 2022, he has been a Research Engineer in Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility with TECNALIA, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Derio, Spain. He was a recipient of the Best Master Thesis on Intelligent Transportation Systems by the Spanish Chapter of the IEEE ITS Society.

JOSE MATUTE received the B.S. degree and M.S. degree in mechanical engineering from Simon Bolivar University, Caracas, Venezuela, in 2008 and 2012, respectively and the Ph.D. degree in control, automation, and robotics engineering from the University of the Basque Country, Leioa, Spain, in 2021. Since 2024, he has been a Senior Robotics Engineer in the Division of Technology Development and Deployment with Virginia Tech Transportation Institute. His research focuses on intelligent transportation systems, particularly au-

tomated driving technologies.

JAVIER ARALUCE (Member, IEEE) received the B.Sc. degree in industrial electronics and automation engineering, the M.Sc. degree in industrial engineering, focused on robotics and perception, and the Ph.D. degree in electronics: advanced electronic systems intelligent systems, from the University of Alcalá, Alcalá de Henares, in 2018, 2020, and 2023, respectively. He is currently a Research Engineer in Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility with TECNALIA, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Derio, Spain.

He has authored or coauthored several works in the main conferences and journals related to autonomous vehicles, robotics, and computer vision. His research interests include deep learning applied to scene understanding and driver attention for intelligent transport systems.

LUKAS KUSCHNIC received the B.Sc. degree in electronics and computer engineering with JOANNEUM University of Applied Sciences, Graz, Austria, in 2017 and the M.Sc. degree in information and computer engineering with a focus on embedded systems and visual computing with the Graz University of Technology, Graz, in 2020. Throughout his professional career, he has primarily been engaged in the ADAS/AD domain. From 2017 to 2020, he was parttime with AVL List GmbH, Graz, as a Development Engineer in ADAS/AD, design-

ing and developing a mobile measurement system capturing dynamic ground truth (DGT). He has been affiliated with the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, Graz, since 2020, working across fields within the AD domain, focusing on sensor integration, environmental perception and simulation to extend and improve the AD platforms.

CHRISTOPH PILZ received the M.Sc. degree in software engineering and management from the Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria, in 2019, and the Ph.D. degree in computer science in the field of automated driving and vehicle to everything communication, focusing on collective perception from the Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria, 2024. Since 2014, he has been with the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, Graz, working across fields within the AD domain. His research interests include creating a simulator for

electronic control units in vehicles, testing perception sensor capabilities and performance, testing and verification of AD software, and analyzing, implementing, and verifying communication security, and building up the competence for vehicle to everything communication.

MARKUS SCHRATTE received the M.Sc. degree in information and computer engineering and the Ph.D. degree in the field of pedestrian collision avoidance system for automated vehicles from the Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria, in 2013 and 2024, respectively. He has been affiliated with the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, Graz, Austria, since 2011 and has been involved across different fields within the ADAS/AD domain as a Senior Researcher. He was with Autonomous Racing Graz as a Technical Lead in 2019 and he

is responsible for the architecture of the autonomous racing stack and the integration of the different subsystems of the racing team. He is currently a Team Leader of the embedded systems demonstrators with Virtual Vehicle. His main task is to develop and integrate systems and concepts into vehicles and robots to bring them to the road, focusing on sensor integration, simulation, software deployment, automated driving software stacks and real world testing.

JOSHUÉ PÉREZ RASTELLI (Member, IEEE) received the B.S. degree in electronic engineering from Simon Bolivar University, Caracas, Venezuela, in 2007, the M.E. degree and the Ph.D. degree from the University Complutense of Madrid, Madrid, Spain, in 2009 and 2012, respectively. He was the Principal Research on Connected and Automated Driving team with Tecnalia Member of the Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Donostia-San Sebastian, Spain, since 2015 to 2024. He moved to the CEIT research center,

also Member of the Basque Research and Technology Alliance. He has more than 17 years of experience in the Intelligent Transportation System field and more than 200 publications related to Connected and Automated Driving and ADAS.

ASIER ZUBIZARRETA received the Ph.D. degree in robotics and automatic control systems with the University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, Leioa, Spain, in 2010. He is currently an Associate Professor with the Department of Automatic Control and Systems Engineering, the Bilbao School of Engineering. His research interests include the development of MPC-based control and development of Soft-Sensors for several applications such as biomedical engineering and manufacturing or automated driving systems.